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**Four new combinations in the genus *Anaches* Pascoe, 1865
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae, Pteropliini)***

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Abstract: Four species, including *Paramesosella medioalba* Breuning, 1956, *Pterolophia albanina* Gressitt, 1942, *Sthenias cylindricus* Gressitt, 1939, and *S. murzini* Lazarev, 2020 are newly combined into the genus *Anaches* Pascoe, 1865, increasing the number of species in this genus to eight.

Introduction

Anaches Pascoe, 1865 was described for *Sthenias dorsalis* Pascoe, 1858, then it was treated as a synonym of the genus *Pterolophia* Newman, 1842 for a long time (Breuning, 1961; Breuning, 1965a; Rondon & Breuning, 1970; Weigel, 2006). Holzschuh & Lin (2013) reinstated the genus, moved *Sthenias semicylindricus* Hayashi, 1974 to this genus and described two new species from Taiwan, China. There were four species in the genus *Anaches* Pascoe, 1865, all distributed in China (Lin & Yang, 2019). Here four species are newly combined into this genus, increasing the number of species to eight.

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Materials and Methods

Specimens are deposited in the following institutions, museums or collections; abbreviations as shown in the text:

BMNH (= NHML): Natural History Museum, London, UK.

CMLR: Collection of M. Lazarev, Moscow, Russia.

IZCAS (= IZAS): Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China.

MNHN: Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France.

MNST: Museum of Natural Science, Taichung, Taiwan, China.

OSAKA: Osaka Museum of Natural History, Osaka, Japan.

ZFMK: Zoologisches Forschungsmuseum "Alexander Koenig", Bonn, Germany.

Taxonomy

Genus *Anaches* Pascoe, 1865

Anaches Pascoe, 1865: 160. Type species: *Sthenias dorsalis* Pascoe, 1858, by original designation.

Diagnosis. *Anaches* Pascoe, 1865 differs from *Pterolophia* Newman, 1842 by the following characters: 1) body slender, elytra more than three times length of pronotum, while the elytra in *Pterolophia* less than three times length of pronotum; 2) prothorax strongly narrower at both base and apex, with the pronotum swollen, while not so or only feebly narrower in *Pterolophia*; 3) in males, first ventrite with long sexual setae at apex, which covering two sexual setal patches on second ventrite, while no such long sexual setae and sexual setal patches in *Pterolophia*; 4) antennae slender and longer, both male and female with antennae longer than body, while antennae in *Pterolophia* stouter, female antennae shorter than body; 5) the fifth antennal segment subequal to the fourth in length, while fifth plus sixth subequal to the fourth in *Pterolophia*.

Anaches Pascoe, 1865 differs from *Sthenias* Dejean, 1835 by the following characters: 1) body slender, elytral length more than three times length of pronotum, while the elytral length less than three times length of pronotum in *Sthenias*; 2) prothorax strongly narrower at both base and apex, with pronotum swollen, while not so or only feebly narrower in *Sthenias* (however, *Sthenias* (*Albosthenias*) *parteaibicollis* Breuning, 1968 has similar prothorax with *Anaches*); 3) each elytron with one tubercle with

tufted hairs before basal one fifth, while such tubercle missing in *Sthenias*; 4) antennae slender and longer, both male and female with antennae longer than body, while antennae in *Sthenias* stouter, female antennae shorter than body; 5) the fifth antennal segment subequal to the fourth in length, while fifth much shorter than fourth in *Sthenias*; 6) antennal fringed hairs beneath not as dense as in *Sthenias*, especially on the apical segments.

Remarks. Based on these characters, 4 species are newly combined into this genus, increasing the number of species to 8.

Holzschuh & Lin (2013) had published such opinion “Außer den drei folgenden Arten, gehören sicherlich noch etliche unter der Gattung *Sthenias* Castelnau, 1848 beschriebenen Arten zu *Anaches* transferiert, wie z.B. *S. cylindricus* Gressitt, 1939, *S. gracilicornis* Gressitt, 1937, *S. gracilis* Breuning, 1938, *S. pictus* Breuning, 1938, *S. pseudodorsalis* Breuning, 1938 oder *S. yunnanus* Breuning, 1938.”. However, all subsequent colleagues did not pay attention to this paragraph and kept all those species in the genus *Sthenias* Dejean, 1835 (Lin, 2014; Lingafelter et al., 2014; Lin, 2015; Lin, Yang, 2019; Lazarev, 2019), so did the Titan database website (access on December 22, 2020). Here we officially publish the new combination of *Anaches cylindricus* (Gressitt, 1939) comb. nov. based on type specimen study, while others will be researched in detail by A. Weigel (personal communication).

Distribution. China, Vietnam, Laos, Thailand, India, Kashmir, Nepal, Bangladesh.

1. *Anaches albaninus* (Gressitt, 1942) comb. nov.

Pterolophia albanina Gressitt, 1942: 85, pl. I, fig. 5. TL China: Zhejiang. TD IZCAS.

Pterolophia (*Hylobrotus*) *albanina*: Breuning, 1961: 252.

Specimens examined. 1 female, holotype, Zhejiang, T'enmushan, 1937-V-21, leg. O. Piel (IZCAS, IOZ(E) 217646); 1 male, Shaanxi, Foping, Longcaoping, alt. 1256 m, 2008-VII-3, leg. Ming Bai (IZCAS); 1 female, Shaanxi, Zhouzhi, Houzhenzi, alt. 1280 m, 2008-V-5-6, leg. Hao Huang (IZCAS); 1 female, Anhui, Huangshan, 1936-VI-24 (IZCAS); 1 male 1 female, Zhejiang, T'ienmushan, 1936-VI-25, leg. O. Piel (IZCAS); 1 female, Tianmushan, 1937-VII-19 (IZCAS); 1 female, Zhejiang, Anji, Longwangshan, alt. 490 m,

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1996-VI-12, leg. Xing-Ke Yang (IZCAS); 1 female, Zhejiang, Lishui, Yujikengbaohuzhan, alt. 1371 m, 27°41'41.77"N, 119°35'26.50"E, 2017-VII-10, leg. Yan-Dong Chen (IZCAS); 1 male, Jiangxi, Ku-ling, 1935-VII-25, leg. O. Piel (IZCAS); 1 male, Fujian, Chong'an, Guadun, 1973-VI-11, leg. Pei-Yu Yu (IZCAS); 1 male 1 female, Fujian, Jianyang, Aotou, 1973-V-27-28, leg. Pei-Yu Yu (IZCAS).

Distribution China: Heilongjiang, Hebei, Henan, Shaanxi, Gansu, Jiangsu, Anhui, Zhejiang, Hubei, Jiangxi, Hunan, Fujian, Guangxi, Sichuan.

2. *Anaches cylindricus* (Gressitt, 1939) comb. nov.

Sthenias cylindricus Gressitt, 1939: 114, pl. III, fig. 7. **TL** China: Zhejiang. **TD** IZCAS.

Specimens examined. 1 male, holotype, Zhejiang, T'ienmushan, 1937-V-31, leg. O. Piel (IZCAS, IOZ(E) 217659).

Distribution. China: Zhejiang, Hunan, Fujian.

3. *Anaches dorsalis* (Pascoe, 1858)

Sthenias dorsalis Pascoe, 1858: 251. **TL** India. **TD** BMNH.

Anaches dorsalis: Pascoe, 1865: 160.

Anaches albonotatus Pic, 1932: 25. **TL** Northern Vietnam (Tonkin). **TD** MNHN. Synonymized by Breuning, 1965a: 203.

Specimens examined. 1 male, Zhejiang, Tianmushan, alt. 350 m, 1999-VI-5, leg. Ming-Yuan Gao (IZCAS, IOZ(E) 1896988); 1 female, Fujian, Huangkeng, 1965-VII (IZCAS); 1 female, Fujian, Jianxi, 1981-IV-21 (IZCAS); 1 male, Sichuan, Emeishan, Qingyinge, alt. 800-1000 m, 1957-VII-4, leg. Fuxing Zhu (IZCAS); 1 female, Guangxi, Jinxiu, Fenzhan, alt. 800 m, 1999-V-13, leg. Hui Xiao (IZCAS, IOZ(E) 1896989); 1 female, Guizhou, Guiyang, Huaxi, 2011-VI (IZCAS).

Distribution. China: Shaanxi, Zhejiang, Fujian, Hong Kong, Guangxi, Chongqing, Sichuan, Guizhou, Yunnan. Vietnam, Laos, Thailand, India (Himachal Pradesh), Kashmir, Nepal, Bangladesh.

4. *Anaches medioalbus* (Breuning, 1956) comb. nov.

Paramesosella medioalba Breuning, 1956: 234. **TL** China: Fujian. **TD** ZFMK.

Specimens examined (through pictures). Holotype, female, Kwangtseh-Fukien, 1937-VIII-19 (ZFMK).

Distribution. China: Fujian.

Remarks. The type locality, Kwangtseh-Fukien, should be translated as Guangze, Fujian, which is nowadays located in Hangchuan zhen, Guangze county, Nanping, Fujian Province (Lampe et al., 2006). It is very similar to *Anaches semicylindricus* (Hayashi, 1974).

5. *Anaches murzini* (Lazarev, 2020) comb. nov.

Sthenias (s. str.) *murzini* Lazarev, 2020: 57, figs. 1-3. **TL** China: Sichuan. **TD** CMLR.

Specimens examined. Holotype, male, China, Sichuan prov., Qingcheng Hou Shan Mts., 70 km NW Chengdu, 1450 m, 2004-VIII-15, leg. S. Murzin (CMLR).

Distribution China: Sichuan.

Remarks. This species is very similar to *Anaches dorsalis* (Pascoe, 1858), but can be easily distinguished by the elytral apex with different shape and the narrow curved white line near apical third with the peak near suture much higher than the peak near lateral margin.

6. *Anaches semicylindricus* (Hayashi, 1974)

Sthenias semicylindricus Hayashi, 1974: 45. **TL** China: Taiwan. **TD** OSAKA.
Anaches semicylindricus: Holzschuh & Lin, 2013: 152.

Distribution. China: Taiwan.

7. *Anaches wenhsini* Holzschuh & Lin, 2013

Anaches wenhsini Holzschuh & Lin, 2013: 152, figs. 8, 9. **TL** China: Taiwan. **TD** MNST.

Specimens examined. 1 male, paratype, Taiwan, Pingtung County, Mt. Dahan, 2007-VII-28, leg. Wenhsin Lin (IZCAS, IOZ(E) 1905281).

Distribution. China: Taiwan.

8. *Anaches yitingi* Holzschuh & Lin, 2013

Anaches yitingi Holzschuh & Lin, 2013: 154, fig. 10. **TL** China: Taiwan. **TD** MNST.

Specimens examined. 1 male 1 female, paratypes, Taiwan, Pingtung County, Mt. Dahan, 2007-V-26, leg. Wenhsin Lin (IZCAS, IOZ(E) 1905283-84).

Distribution China: Taiwan.

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